
Research Article

New combination in *Ibatia* (Apocynaceae, Asclepiadoideae, Asclepiadeae)

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Abstract: A new combination is proposed here for *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail under the genus *Ibatia* Decne. as *Ibatia holtonii* (Vail) R.Kr.Singh, Arigela & Sanjeet Kumar. Additionally, to fix the identity and to avoid the misapplication of name *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail, a lectotype is designated here.

Keywords: Colombia, Endemic, *Ibatia holtonii*, Lectotype, *Stelmagonum holtonii*

Introduction

The genus *Ibatia* Decne. consists of about 36 species, distributed in tropical America (POWO, 2025). In Colombia, the genus is represented by six species, namely *I. cumanensis* (Willd. ex Schult.) Morillo, *I. dugandii* (Krings) Morillo, *I. fontana* (Saville & Krings) Morillo, *I. holtonii* (Vail) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *I. maritima* (Jacq.) Decne. and *I. rubra* (H.Karst.) Morillo, of which *I. dugandii* and *I. holtonii* are endemic.

Morillo (Phytoneuron 2015-22: 2. 2015) proposed a new combination for *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail under the genus *Ibatia* as *I. holtonii* (Vail) Morillo. However, this combination is invalid under Article 36.3 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018), as he simultaneously proposed an alternative new combination for the same taxon under the genus *Matelea* Aubl. as *Matelea holtonii* (Vail) Morillo in the same publication and on the same page. Consequently, both names are considered alternative names and are therefore invalid.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail (NY00318783, © Herbarium of New York Botanical Garden)

Here, we propose a valid new combination for *Stelmagonum holtonii* under the genus *Ibatia* as *Ibatia holtonii* (Vail) R.Kr.Singh, Arigela & Sanjeet Kumar. In accordance with Article 9 of the Shenzhen Code (Turland et al., 2018), a lectotype is designated for the name *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail.

New combination

Ibatia holtonii (Vail) R.Kr.Singh, Arigela & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Stelmagonum holtonii* Vail, Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 26(8): 424. 1899. *Ibatia holtonii* (Vail) Morillo, Phytoneuron 2015-22: 2. 2015, *nom. altern. et inval.* *Matelea holtonii* (Vail) Morillo, Phytoneuron 2015-22: 2. 2015, *nom. altern. et inval.*

Lectotype (designated here): Colombia, New Grenada, Magdalena, December 1842, *I.F. Holton 461* (NY00318783!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Endemic to Colombia.

Notes: In the protologue of *Stelmagonum holtonii*, Vail (1899) mentioned the type information as “*New Grenada*: Goudot; Flora Neogranadina-Magdalena, I. E. Holton, Opia, no. 461, Dec., 1852. Both of these specimens are in the Kew Herbarium and a duplicate of the Holton number is in the Herbarium of Columbia University”. Pertaining to this type specification, one specimen for the name *S. holtonii* Vail is traced at NY (NY00318783), and is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

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